

Moraxella

750000

500000

250000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Laribacter

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aquaspirillum

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pelagibaca

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aeromonas

1500000

1000000

500000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Nibricoccus

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Gallibacterium

Conchiformibus

12000
9000
6000
3000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chlorobium

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Simonsiella

Melaminivora

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Desulfococcus

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rhizobacter

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Klebsiella

Desulfobacter

6e+05
4e+05
2e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bibersteinia

80000
60000
40000
20000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Candidatus.Babela

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sphaerotilus

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Tolumonas

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Acidovorax

2e+06

1e+06

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Diaphorobacter

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Selenomonas

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Glaesserella

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Desulfosarcina

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Anaerostipes

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aquabacterium

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Comamonas

$2e+05$

$1e+05$

$0e+00$

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Methylomusa

10000

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Vitreoscilla

50000

40000

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pseudobutyrvibrio

20000
15000
10000
5000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aggregatibacter

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rubrivivax

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Phocaeicola

1500000
1000000
500000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Denitrotribrio

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Actinobacillus

10000

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Roseburia

90000

60000

30000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Streptobacillus

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sporomusa

4000
3000
2000
1000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Leptotrichia

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Parabacteroides

2e+05

1e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Flintibacter

Ottowia

3e+05

2e+05

1e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bernardetia

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pseudoleptotrichia

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Veillonella

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rheinheimera

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Limnohabitans

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Snodgrassella

4000
2000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Thiomonas

50000

40000

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Oscillibacter

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chryseobacterium

Sebaldella

60000
40000
20000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Candidatus.Saccharimonas

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Megasphaera

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Adhaeribacter

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sphaerochaeta

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Blastochloris

9000

6000

3000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sulfuritortus

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Christensenella

Fusobacterium

200000
150000
100000
50000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Alkalitalea

2e+05

1e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Flavonifractor

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Butyrivibrio

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Methylomicrobium

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Lachnoclostridium

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Caldimicrobium

Paraprevotella

40000

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Anaerolinea

10000

5000

0

0 100 200 300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Lachnoanaerobaculum

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Phascolarctobacterium

12000

8000

4000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Mediterraneibacter

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Anaerobutyricum

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Spiroplasma

Candidatus.Nanosynbacter

20000
15000
10000
5000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Faecalitalea

6000
4000
2000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Desulfotomaculum

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Rhodomicrobium

20000
15000
10000
5000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Kiritimatiella

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Petrocella

4000

3000

2000

1000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sulfurospirillum

2000000
1500000
1000000
500000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Acutalibacter

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Caproiciproducens

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Glaciecola

8000
6000
4000
2000
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sulfurihydrogenibium

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chitinibacter

7500
5000
2500
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Francisella

Acinetobacter

2e+06

1e+06

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Mesorhizobium

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Cruoricator

3000

2000

1000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Eubacterium

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Ruthenibacterium

9000

6000

3000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Photobacterium

Prevotella

3e+05

2e+05

1e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Ethanoligenens

Aequorivita

Undibacterium

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Janibacter

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pseudoxanthomonas

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Lachnospira

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Saliniradius

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Desulfobacula

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Ruminococcus

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pulveribacter

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Methylobacterium

9e+05
6e+05
3e+05
0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Riemerella

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Thermodesulfobacterium

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aminomonas

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sulfuricum

Defluviitoga

1e+05

5e+04

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Schlegelella

Enterobacter

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Polynucleobacter

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hydrogenophilus

2000

1000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Methylorubrum

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Dechloromonas

1e+06
5e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Saccharospirillum

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Polaromonas

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chitinolyticbacter

8000
6000
4000
2000
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Heliobacterium

7500
5000
2500
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Erysipelatoclostridium

6000
4000
2000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Curvibacter

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Thermoclostridium

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Adlercreutzia

9000

6000

3000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Escherichia

6e+05

4e+05

2e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Anaerocolumnna

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Synechococcus

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pannonibacter

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pandoraea

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chitinimonas

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Psychrobacter

Providencia

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bacteriovorax

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Nitratiruptor

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Ereboglobus

Desulfobivrio

Rhodopseudomonas

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Odoribacter

3e+05

2e+05

1e+05

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Epilithonimonas

Terricaulis

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Nitrosomonas

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Fibroacter

Cloacibacterium

1500000

1000000

500000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Sulfuriferula

Defluviicoccus

50000
40000
30000
20000
10000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hungatella

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Geobacter

6e+05
4e+05
2e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Shewanella

1500000
1000000
500000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Mannheimia

3000

2000

1000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Mycobacterium

40000

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Burkholderia

1e+06
5e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Thermosulfuriphilus

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bordetella

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Dysosmobacter

4000
2000
0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Mucinivorans

80000

60000

40000

20000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Acetoanaerobium

60000
40000
20000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Clostridium

100000

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Chloracidobacterium

3e+05
2e+05
1e+05
0e+00

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Tenacibaculum

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Draconibacterium

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Leptospira

15000
10000
5000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Turneriella

Oceanhabitans

Sinimariniibacterium

7500

5000

2500

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Pusillimonas

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Monoglobus

6000
4000
2000
0

0 100 200 300
Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Serpentinomonas

20000

15000

10000

5000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Bdellovibrio

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Citrobacter

1e+05

5e+04

0e+00

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Hylemonella

12000

8000

4000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Candidatus.Endolissoclinum

6000

4000

2000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Aliarcobacter

100000

75000

50000

25000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Antarcticibacterium

50000

40000

30000

20000

10000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

Desulfurobacterium

150000

100000

50000

0

0

100

200

300

Days_from_AUG_3_2020

